

Quantifying chloride resistance of concrete from cement paste-scale tests

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Concrete is a material with intrinsically low environmental impact compared to other construction materials. However, the enormous volumes of cement and concrete usage leads to cement-based materials accounting for around 8% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. To reduce these emissions, replacing Portland cement clinker with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) has been a successful strategy. Although several studies focused on the mechanical performance of clinker substitution, there are concerns regarding the rapid assessment of long-term durability performance of a given cement composition. This study aims to address these concerns by linking the chloride resistance of both concrete and cement paste scales, by leveraging the assumption that durability of concrete is a strong function of binder composition. Accelerated steady-state migration and bulk resistivity tests were conducted at both paste and concrete scales on a diverse set of binders; the binders include SCMs such as fly ash, slag, natural pozzolan, limestone, calcined clay, and recycled concrete fines. The limits of applicability of the correlation between steady-state diffusion coefficient and bulk resistivity were identified for all the systems at both cement paste and concrete scales. In addition, threshold values to characterize chloride ingress resistance of concrete were proposed based on bulk resistivity and mini-migration diffusion coefficient of pastes. Overall, this study aims to quantify the chloride resistance of concrete from the cement paste-scale tests, thereby accelerating the adoption of low-carbon cement blends.